

I-CLAIM

Improving the Living
and Labour Conditions
of Irregularised Migrant
Households in Europe

Public understanding and attitudes to irregular migration in Poland

Country report

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Executive Summary

The report presents an analysis of the I-CLAIM survey on public opinion on irregular migration and individuals with irregular work and/or residence in Poland (irregularised migrants). The survey was conducted by YouGov between 12 and 23 February 2025 with a nationally representative sample of 1,013 respondents. The study shows that the perception of irregular migration is significantly influenced by mainstream narratives and images that strengthen negative convictions and emotions of threat, despite the increasing social contact with migrants on a daily basis and in the workplace. The survey's key findings show that, while the general perception of migration is not very negative, the majority of respondents viewed irregular migration as a serious issue in Poland and seemed to overestimate the number of irregularised migrants. The findings on integration assessment demonstrate some persistence of racialisation, as some individual attributes were evaluated more positively for irregularised migrants from Ukraine than from India. However, in assessing integration, other factors also played an important role: the level of knowledge of the Polish language, the location of the migrants' family and their marital status (as singles were perceived more negatively). In terms of hiring preferences, the results present a complex picture of attitudes towards migrants; however, what mainly transpires is the negative perceptions of irregularised migrants from Uzbekistan, the greater likelihood of hiring candidates from the Philippines and Ukraine and the importance of the length of residence and location of the family in Poland.

Most survey respondents link access to employment with legal residence status and the need to fill labour shortages. Irregular employment was mainly associated with construction/renovation, agriculture, transportation, food delivery and taxi sectors for men – and with cleaning, catering and hospitality, childcare/elderly care, retail and sex work for women.

The survey depicts that irregular migration is primarily associated with threats and insecurity, which corresponds to the media and political portrayal of migration as an undefined, large-scale 'inflow' often associated with aggression from migrants. The respondents in our survey the most frequently identify irregularities in crossing the border and in the procedure for obtaining international protection. Such a framing of irregular migration affects the latency of integration-related topics. Our research shows that protection as a reason for migration was evaluated less positively than education, yet more positively than migration for economic purposes.

The survey provides a new perspective on the existing research on public opinion by focusing on the aspect of irregular migration. It can serve as a resource for stakeholders, academia and the media working on migration and integration issues.

1. Introduction

Irregular migration has become a highly politicised issue in Poland relatively recently – used by politicians in the context of political struggles, especially in the rivalry between the parties forming the ruling Civic Coalition and the right-wing opposition which governed Poland between 2015 and 2023 (Matuszczyk, Grzymała-Kazłowska and Homel-Ficenes, 2024). Narratives of irregular migration are also highly prevalent in the mass media – especially in the context of border crossings, which are primarily framed as a threat – where migrants are often portrayed as unidentified ‘Others’, homogeneous and dehumanised groups (Homel-Ficenes and Grzymała-Kazłowska, 2025).

The results of the survey align with recent studies conducted in Poland on public attitudes toward migration, integration and migrants (IPSOS, 2025; Roguska, 2025; Scovil, 2025a, 2025b, 2025c). These studies reveal that public opinion is divided regarding the perceived impact of migration on the Polish labour market and the social welfare system. While 69% of Poles believe that migrants place a burden on the welfare system, 48% acknowledge the significant contribution of migrant labour to the country’s economic development (Roguska, 2025). Recent studies also show that Poles have a more negative perception of the term ‘immigrant’ than of ‘foreigner’ (Scovil, 2025b) and that the assimilation-oriented model of integration (Scovil, 2025a) prevails in public opinion, with a high level of significance attached to Polish language proficiency for evaluating integration.

Despite their salience, the issues of irregular migration and the different forms of work and residence irregularities of migrants have been very little examined in terms of public perceptions. Social attitudes are, however, a significant part of ‘irregularity assemblage’ (Sigona and van Liempt, 2025), which demonstrates how irregularity is produced as an effect of the intersections of migration laws, policies and practices, labour market and welfare systems, dominant narratives and perceptions, as well as how it is experienced by migrants.

To better understand public perceptions on this issue, the Horizon Europe-funded project ‘Improving the Living and Labour Conditions of Irregularised Migrant Households in Europe’ (I-CLAIM), in collaboration with YouGov, carried out a nationally representative survey in February 2025. This report, using a similar template across all I-CLAIM countries, analyses this survey and aims to answer two main questions:

- 1) What does the public know about irregular migration and irregularised migrants?
- 2) What are public attitudes toward irregular migration and irregularised migrants within the context of work?

In general, our survey shows that, although migration as such is not perceived as Poland’s key concern, our respondents stress its burdens more than its benefits, with evaluations of its cultural impacts being more mixed. Irregular migration is regarded as a challenge by the majority of the respondents, who also considerably overestimate its scale. Irregularity is predominantly associated with border crossings, applications for international protection and being hired by recruitment agencies. Most respondents said that work should be allowed for migrants whose residence is legalised and for whom there is a demand for their job on the labour market. The hiring experiment, featuring the vignettes of migrants from Ukraine, Uzbekistan and the Philippines, demonstrated generally more favourable attitudes towards Ukrainian migrants than towards those from outside Europe, with candidates from Uzbekistan being the least desired as employees. However, when, among men, there was only a negative likelihood of hiring someone from Uzbekistan, women also demonstrated a negative preference towards Ukrainian migrants. Across all age groups, there was a negative attitude towards hiring someone from Uzbekistan and a positive likelihood of hiring candidates from Ukraine and the Philippines, with

the oldest group preferring the former and the youngest the latter. The experiment on perceptions of integration demonstrated a presumably racialising effect of social othering, with the integration of a hypothetical migrant from India being less positively assessed than that of someone from Ukraine (similarly described). Nevertheless, like the hiring experiment, women and the youngest respondents evaluated the integration of the Ukrainian migrant less favourably than the Indian one.

The report consists of a methodological section outlining information on the survey, our sample and our analysis, followed by a study of public attitudes towards irregular migration and irregularised migrants in general, as well as in the context of work. Our analysis focuses on the roles of gender, age and political views in perceptions of irregularity related to migrants and migration.

2. About the Survey

2.1. Development and methodology

The I-CLAIM survey set out to explore how Polish adults perceive and respond to issues of irregular migration and irregular status concerning work and residence. The survey was conducted online by YouGov to capture public attitudes toward irregular migration and irregularised migrants, as well as broader views on immigration, alongside key socio-demographic data through a combination of ‘traditional’ survey questions and survey experiments.¹

The questionnaire was jointly designed by the I-CLAIM consortium during dedicated workshops. It comprised six thematic blocks and 25 items (see Appendix Table A.1) and underwent pilot-testing before launch. Demographic variables were drawn from existing YouGov panel data and integrated into the final dataset (see Abraham, 2025 for further details).

2.2. Target population, sample and fieldwork

The survey targeted adults living in Poland, with respondents selected from YouGov’s panel using ‘targeted quota sampling’ (Abraham, 2025). YouGov applied the following factors in order for the sample to be representative of the adult Polish population: age; gender and education level, vote at the 2023 Parliamentary Election 2023 and region, location and level of political interest. Sampling weights taking these factors into account were provided and used in all analyses. Responses from a total of 1,031 respondents were collected between 12 and 23 February 2025.

¹ Survey experiments, which are becoming increasingly popular in migration research (Sobolewska and Lessard-Phillips, 2024) are designed to measure public attitudes by systematically varying question wording or attributes to assess how specific factors influence responses.

2.3. Data analysis

All analyses were conducted in Stata, applying the provided sample weights to ensure representativeness. For descriptive statistics, categorical data were summarised using frequency distributions (ensuring that no cell had a count under 5), while continuous measures were reported as means with standard deviations. Group differences were assessed through chi-squared tests, differences in proportions and differences in means. Experimental results were analysed using Average Marginal Components Effects (AMCEs) (Hainmueller et al., 2014) and Marginal Means (MMs) (Leeper et al., 2020) to capture attribute effects and subgroup preferences. Cases with missing responses were excluded from specific analyses, resulting in varying sample sizes across items.

2.4. Survey respondents' main characteristics

This section presents an overview of the key respondent characteristics of the sample. Supporting tables are in the appendix (Tables A.2–A.4). The main demographic profiles of respondents are summarised in Table A.2 and discussed here. The mean age of the sample was 46.4 years (not shown in the table), while 41.7% were adults in the 18–39 category, 30.6% were between 40 and 64 and 27.7% were 65 and older; 51.2% of respondents were female and 48.8% male. The vast majority of respondents (over 95.2%) reported not being members of a minority ethnic group. Most respondents (69.7%) were married or partnered. The distribution between urban and rural residence was relatively even: 48% of survey respondents reported living in urban areas, while 52% lived in rural areas. In terms of geographical distribution across Poland, more respondents resided in the central and southern regions (21.5% and 20.3%, respectively), followed by the eastern (17.5%), north-western (15.8%), northern (14.8%) and south-western (10.1%) regions.²

In terms of socio-demographic characteristics (Table A.3), 9.7% of the respondents reported having low levels of education (up to lower-secondary), 65.9% having medium levels of education (upper-secondary to short-cycle tertiary) and 24.5% having high levels of education (Bachelors'+).

Just over 53.7% of respondents were in work (either full- or part-time), while 46.3% of them indicated that they were not working for various reasons (e.g. studies, retirement, child/family care, unemployment status). In terms of economic situation, 29.5% reported a low gross household income (up to 4,000 PLN per month), 40.1% a medium household income (4,001–8,000 PLN per month) and 30.4% a high level of household income (8,001+ PLN per month).

Among those who voted in the 2023 parliamentary elections, our respondents casted their vote for right-wing *Law and Justice/United Right (Prawo i Sprawiedliwość, PIS/Zjednoczona Prawica)* (29.9%), followed by the liberal-centrist alliance Civic Coalition (*Koalicja Obywatelska, KO*) (25.2%) (including Civic Platform (*Platforma Obywatelska, PO*) and small parties such as Modern (*Nowoczesna/.N*), Polish Initiative (*Inicjatywa Polska*) and the Greens (*Partia Zieloni*)), the Third Way (*Trzecia Droga*) alliance (consisting of a new liberal-centrist party Poland 2050 (*Polska 2050*) and the agrarian-centrist Polish Peasant Party (*Polskie Stronnictwo Ludowe, PSL*) (12%), the New Left (*Nowa Lewica*) alliance (8%) and a radical-right free-market alliance, Confederation (*Konfederacja*) (5.9%) (the parties' classification based on Szczerbiak, 2025). Those who voted for other parties accounted for 3%, while a substantial number (15.8%) indicated invalid votes or selected the 'did not know' answer. After eight years of the Law and Justice rule, the current coalition government consists of KO, PSL, Poland 2020 and the New Left.

² The division was applied in accordance with the NUTS 1 (macroregions) classification, Statistics Office (GUS), <https://stat.gov.pl/en/regional-statistics/classification-of-territorial-units/classification-of-territorial-units-for-statistics-nuts/the-nuts-classification-in-poland/>

We also asked for the respondents' own links to – and experiences with – migration (Table A.4), measured as being born outside Poland (3%), having at least one parent born outside Poland (4%), having some experience of living abroad for at least a year (13%) and having immigrant friends (33.6%).

The characteristics provide an overview of the sample as well as the main subgroups to compare when detailing knowledge and attitudes toward irregular migration and irregularised migrants. In this report, we focus on gender (male/female), age group (18–39; 40–64; 65+) and political views perceived through the party voted for at the 2023 parliamentary elections (United Right, Civic Coalition, Third Way, Other).³

3. Views towards Immigration

We start with general opinions about immigrants and immigration, as they have been deemed to be important when contextualising attitudes toward irregular migration and irregularised migrants. Other survey research in Poland, for example, shows associations between immigrants and 'illegal' border crossing and criminality (Scovil, 2025b).

Respondents were asked to evaluate the main areas of concern for Poland and for themselves. Of the nine predefined policy areas, the highest levels of concern were reported for health (70.9%), the economy (61.2%), defence (52.4%) and housing (25.8%). Immigration was mentioned as a national concern by 24.9% of people who contributed to the survey, followed by education (23%) and the environment (20.3%). In terms of personal assessment, immigration was identified as a concern by 18.7% of respondents, ranking third among the least-frequently selected areas, after transport (16.6%) and crime (14.8%). Similar to the evaluation of national concerns, the largest share (74.8%) found the issue of health to be personally relevant.

Emulating questions from the European Social Survey (Heath et al., 2016), respondents were also asked about the perceived costs and benefits of migration with regards to whether immigrants take out more than they put in – in terms of taxes and services (Figure 1) – and whether the country's cultural life was undermined or enriched by immigrants (Figure 2). Responses were recorded on a scale from 0 (more negative view) to 10 (more positive view) and grouped into three categories: negative view (scores of 0–4), neutral view (score 5) and positive view (scores 6–10). Variations across main subgroups (gender, age and political affiliation) were also examined.

Figure 1 indicates that, with regards to contributions toward tax and services, opinions were divided: 45.2% of respondents believed that immigrants take out more than they contribute in taxes and services (negative view), while 34.6% considered that immigrants contribute more than they receive (positive view). Views differed between men and women: more women (50.9%) expressed negative opinions, while men were more divided, with 39.5% expressing negative and 40% expressing positive views.

Quite surprisingly, differences across age groups indicated that adults aged 18–39 years had a more negative outlook (48.4%), with the oldest group expressing the relatively least negative attitude (37.6%). From the perspective of political affiliation, those voting for the Third Way had the most negative outlook (55.9%), followed by no voters/undefined (50.4%), United Right (45.75%) and Civic Coalition (41.9%). The negative views of the proportion of Third Way voters' were significantly higher than those of respondents voting for other parties (37.7%). The highest negativity of the Third Way voters may be linked to the fact that this political alliance consists of the Polish Peasant Party and the centrist Poland 2025 party.

³ Further on in the report, the category 'Other' means those who voted for other parties such as the New Left and Confederation.

Such ambiguity in the perception of the benefits and costs of migration corresponds with the recent results of the CBOS polling survey on the perceived presence of migrants (Roguska, 2025), which demonstrated that over half of the respondents acknowledged migrants' contribution to the national budget and their role in supporting an ageing population, while almost 70% stated that migrants place a burden on the social welfare system.

Figure 1: Perceived costs and benefits of migration among I-CLAIM survey respondents: immigrant take out/put in more (taxes and services). Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025). Baseline N=891.

Regarding whether Polish culture was undermined or enriched by immigrants, 43.3% of respondents had a positive outlook, while 39.4% had a negative one. Positive and negative attitudes were distributed relatively evenly by gender: 44.3% of men and 42.3% of women held positive views, while 39.5% of men and 39.3% of women held negative opinions. Older respondents appeared to have a more positive outlook than the youngest respondents, with those in the different age groups reporting a 52.7% (65+), 44% (40–64) and 36.7% (18–39) positive assessment, which proves consistency between the perception of so-called realistic and symbolic threats across different age groups (according to Stephan and Stephan, 2000, realistic threats are those perceived as concerning physical and material existence, whereas symbolic ones are linked to differences in values, beliefs and attitudes). Respondents who voted for the United Right (45%) and those for whom no voting information was held (45.6%) tended to hold more negative views than those voting the Third way (43.4% – not significantly different) and Civic Coalition (31.1%).

Figure 2: Perceived costs and benefits of migration among I-CLAIM survey respondents: Cultural life undermined/enriched by immigrants. Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025). Baseline N=927.

4. Main Results

We now turn to providing answers to the main questions of the report: 1. *What does the public know about irregular migration and irregularised migrants?* [knowledge section] and 2. *What are public attitudes toward irregular migration and irregular migrants within the context of work?* [attitudes section]. The findings are presented first in terms of overall patterns and then of breakdowns by gender, age and the party voted for.

4.1. Knowledge of irregular migration and irregularised migrants

The following section presents findings on respondents' understanding of irregular migration and the situation of irregularised migrants in Poland. First, respondents were asked to estimate the scale of irregular migration and the level of concern about it in Polish society. Secondly, the survey asked about perceptions of the circumstances that may lead to an irregularised status. Thirdly, it focused on labour-related issues, examining which employment sectors are the most-commonly associated with irregular migrant work and assessing attitudes and perceived social distance towards people with non-regular statuses working in Poland.

4.1.1 Scale and level of concern

Perceptions of the scale of irregular migration reveal the public's limited knowledge, as well as the impact of popular and media discourses. To estimate perceptions of irregular migration in Poland, respondents were asked to assess the share of migrants with an irregular residence status among all the people born outside Poland but residing there. In the survey, the definition of migrants with an irregular residence status was provided as *'a foreign national living in Poland who does not have the legal right to reside in the country'*.

The survey results were compared with some expert estimates of the number of irregularised migrants in Poland from the project 'Measuring Irregular Migration' (MIRREM), which range from 1.2% to 9.9% of the foreign population (Kierans and Vargas-Silvas 2025). For the comparison with expert estimations, three categories were applied: more than 10% above the estimated range; up to 10% above the estimated range; and below, on or around the estimated range (see Figures 3 and 4).

We can see in Figure 3 that the majority of respondents (92.6%) overestimated the share of irregularised migrants in the country, with almost 80% indicating a figure more than 10% higher than the estimated number of migrants – and only 7.4% within and below the estimated range. Women were more likely than men to overestimate by more than 10% and less likely to choose 'below the estimated range' or 'on/around the estimated range'. The middle-aged group was the most likely to overestimate by more than 10%, followed by the youngest group aged 18–39 years. Variation was also observed across political affiliations, with Third Way voters and those who did not vote/did not reveal their political preferences, followed by United Right voters, the most highly overestimating the numbers of irregularised migrants. Respectively 87.7%, 86.4% and 83.2% of the above-mentioned provided answers which were more than 10% above the estimated range, while this was the case for 73.9% of Civic Coalition supporters and 71.1% of those voting for other parties (as diverse as the political alliance the New Left and the radical right-wing Confederation).

Figure 3: Perception of the scale of irregular migration in Poland compared to estimates.
Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025). Baseline N=773.

Respondents were also asked to indicate how much of a concern they considered irregular migration to be in Poland, using a scale from 0 (not a concern at all) to 10 (a very significant concern). Figure 4 shows the proportion of respondents who rated irregular migration as an important concern (i.e., scoring above 5 on the scale). Overall, 77.2% of respondents viewed irregular migration as a serious issue in Poland. This view was less common among those aged 65 and over (67.9%) compared to the youngest voters (78.5%) and particularly to the middle-age group (84%). Irregular migration was seen as a serious concern by all voters, mostly by voters of the United Right (82.3%) and, lastly, by supporters of Civic Coalition (72.9%) – but these differences were not statistically significant.

Figure 4: Irregular migration as a concern for Poland.
Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025). Baseline N=946.

4.1.2 Becoming 'irregularised': testing scenarios

The survey explored respondents' perceptions and knowledge of possible paths of irregularity. Respondents were asked to estimate possible links (most/all of the time; never/sometimes; uncertain) between the lack of residence status with six suggested scenarios: 1. 'Crossing a border without proper documentation'; 2. 'Waiting to hear about their asylum claim'; 3. 'Being hired through a recruitment company'; 4. 'Having an expired student visa'; 5. 'Being a worker from the UK in Poland'; 6. 'Being born in Poland to parents who do not have legal residence status'.

As Table 1 demonstrates, irregularity was mainly associated with unauthorised border crossings. This finding aligns with our research on media and public narratives of irregular migration in Poland, indicating that media coverage of migration has been dominated by messages about border crossings and the humanitarian crisis at the Polish–Belarusian border (Homel-Ficenes and Grzymała-Kazłowska, 2025). Almost equally as popular were associations of irregularity with those waiting to hear about their asylum claim and being hired through a recruitment company. The former may be explained by the public's lack of knowledge about the rights of people applying for protection and by the complexity of administrative processes and their limited coverage of migration-related issues in Poland. Although the Act of 13 June 2003 on Granting Protection to Foreigners within the Territory of the Republic of Poland states that applying for

international protection ensures a legal stay until the proceedings are finally concluded, the perception of the potential ‘irregularity’ of applicants under protection procedures may derive from media portrayals of people seeking protection as a threat perpetuated by external actors (e.g. the Belarusian and Russian regimes), as well as from political decisions legitimising pushbacks and suspending the acceptance of applications for international protection. The visibility of the association of irregularity with ‘being hired through a recruitment agency’ may be linked, on the one hand, to the widespread popularity of employment agencies in Poland and, on the other, to the limited presence of employment-related topics that would normalise migrants’ presence in public and media discourse. Another scenario, ‘having an expired student visa’, was considered a less likely pathway to irregularity than those mentioned above, although more likely than being a child born in Poland to foreigners without residence status or being a worker from the UK in Poland, with the latter regarded as highly uncertain. These results suggest that perceptions of irregular migration may be strongly influenced by mass media and political discourse, especially in the context of Poland’s recent transition from an emigration to an immigration country (Okólski, 2021). In the light of highly politicised narratives, people may not understand the different aspects of migration, such as the situation of international students or UK workers in the European Union or the experiences of the second generation of migrants, as they may have little knowledge of or contact with these groups.

		Likelihood of scenario leading to irregularity		Uncertainty regarding scenario (N=1,013)
		Never/Sometimes	Most/all of the time	
S c e n a r i o s	Crossing border without documentation (N=826)	46.2%	53.8%	20%
	Waiting to hear about their asylum claim (N=792)	48.6%	51.4%	23%
	Being hired through a recruitment company (N=763)	48.9%	51.1%	24.8%
	Having an expired student visa (N=728)	59.9%	40.1%	28.3%
	Being a worker from the UK in the EU (N=553)	68.2%	31.8%	46%
	Being born in Poland to parents who do not have legal residence status (N=709)	68.5%	31.5%	30.1%

Table 1. Scenarios of irregularity.
Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025).

We also examined group differences in evaluations of the scenarios. When it comes to the border crossings without relevant documents (Figure 5), the responses were relatively similar across the different participant groups. However, men, people 65+ and voters for the United Right and Third Way all expressed the strongest convictions that such a situation leads to irregularity (although these views were not significantly different to those of other groups), while respondents who voted for other parties identified, less than others, that this scenario was likely to lead to irregularity.

Figure 5. Evaluation of the scenarios leading to irregularity: crossing a border without documentation. Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025).

The scenario which included being under asylum procedure (see Figure 6) also had very few differences across the groups of respondents. It is, again, voters of other parties who tended to think of this scenario as being less likely, especially compared to United Right and Civic Coalition voters. Even if not statistically significant, this scenario was associated with irregularity more strongly by younger participants (18–39), women and Civic Coalition voters. In contrast, among the middle-aged (40–64), the largest share of respondents (51.9%) considered this scenario unlikely to lead to irregularity.

Figure 6. Evaluation of the scenarios leading to irregularity: waiting to hear about an asylum claim. Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025).

In the cases of a child born in Poland to parents without regulated residence status, as well as UK workers in the EU (see Figures 7 and 8), this scenario was more commonly chosen among younger adults (18–39) and among the Third Way and United Right electorate (although differences across parties were not statistically significant). This confirms the observations from the I-CLAIM project and other studies in Poland which point to the shift, instead, towards anti-migration attitudes among younger groups (Feliksiak, 2023; Scovil 2025b).

Figure 7. Evaluation of the scenarios leading to irregularity: children born to parents without legal residence. Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025).

Finally, we look at one of the scenarios which was less often identified with irregularity: that of being a UK worker in the EU (31.8% identification as likely). There is, again, relative agreement between groups. The only statistically significant difference in views is between younger (38.7%) and older adults (24.8%) respondents. United Right voters also had the highest percentage of those who identified this scenario as being likely.

Figure 8. Evaluation of the scenarios leading to irregularity: UK workers in the EU. Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025).

As the results show, the scenarios primarily associated with irregularity were those linked to entering the country and waiting for a status in the asylum procedure, while other scenarios were less prominent in respondents' perceptions. This offers important insights into how the public understanding of irregularity is produced and reinforced through emotionally charged media and political narratives (Homel-Ficenes and Grzymała-Kazłowska, 2025).

4.2 Irregularised migrants and work: sectors and overall feelings

When evaluating access to the labour market, the majority of respondents (54.7%) linked the possibility of working to having legal residence and performing work that fills labour-market gaps. Only 16.8% of respondents indicated that migrants should be allowed to work regardless of their legal residence status. Restricting the right to work only to situations involving a labour-market gap was indicated by 14.3%. Over 10% stated that migrants should not be allowed to work without legal residence while fewer than 4% felt that migrants should not be allowed to work at all.

Survey respondents were also asked to indicate the sectors in which, in their opinion, irregularised migrants are likely to work. Interestingly, the results revealed similarities between assessing irregular employment among migrants and the general characteristics of informal work in Poland emerging from data on unregistered employment, as well as subjective assessment of work performed in the hidden economy (GUS, 2024). As the Statistics Office showed, in 2022, renovation and construction, agriculture and cleaning were the top three types of work performed as undeclared work for households (GUS, 2024: 26).

For male migrants, the most frequently mentioned sectors were construction and renovation, agriculture, transportation and food delivery. In contrast, women's work was the most often associated with cleaning and domestic services, catering and hospitality, childcare, elderly care and retail.

	First	Second	Third	Fourth
Male	Construction/renovation	Agriculture	Transportation	Food delivery
Female	Cleaning and other	Catering and hospitality	Child/elderly care	Retail

*Table 2. Main sectors in which irregular migrants are deemed to work.
Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025).*

Although a list of sectors was provided, respondents to this question could also indicate additional areas which, in their view, are characterised by the irregular employment of foreigners. The free-text responses showed that respondents often associated such work with taxi services, including platform-based driving (e.g., Uber drivers). Several survey respondents also stated that migrants 'do not work', which may reflect negative attitudes related to the previously discussed question about the perceived social impact of migration. When referring to migrant women's work, respondents the most frequently additionally mentioned sex work and factory production.

To assess indicators of social distance, survey respondents were asked to rate, on a scale from 0 (would not mind at all) to 10 (would mind a great deal), their opinions about having contact with migrants without regular legal status in three contexts: (1) as a person hired to undertake domestic work or repairs at home, (2) as a co-worker employed by the same company and (3) as a person providing services in a shop or restaurant. As illustrated in Figure 9, the mean social distance scores are reported for the overall sample and its subgroups, with higher values indicating greater social distance.

Figure 9. Social distance indicators.
 Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025). Baseline Ns=887/894/914.

Social distance was the least pronounced in public settings such as shops and the highest in private (home) or work environments. In contexts of more direct or personal contact, such as the private space of the home or the workplace, the expressed greater social distance was quite often undistinguishable as the mean levels were quite similar (data points overlapping). Lower levels of social distance were reported in all cases among older survey respondents (65+). Higher levels among younger groups in the workplace may reflect concerns about employment opportunities in Poland or the perceived sense of competition (Roguska, 2025). Considering political preferences, voters supporting the United Right expressed the highest levels of social distance.

4.3 Attitudes

In the next section, we discuss findings from two experimental components of the survey: one investigating respondents’ preferences related to the possibility to employ a migrant with irregular legal status, and the other assessing perceptions of their integration within Polish society.

4.3.1 Hiring choice

The first experiment focused on the hypothetical chances of hiring a female and a male migrant to provide care support for a relative. This corresponds with previously mentioned survey results whereby care services are associated with a higher likelihood of migrants’ irregular employment. Respondents were asked to consider, among two pairs of candidates, the probability of choosing the person they were more likely to hire, even though that person could not provide proof of residence in Poland. In this experiment, respondents were asked to assess the likelihood of hiring each candidate and to indicate which they would prefer to hire. The profiles differed across several dimensions, including the country of origin and corresponding name (Ukraine, the Philippines and Uzbekistan were used to reflect current migration trends in Poland), as well as length of residence in Poland (under one year or five years), presence of a recommendation (none or the recommendation of a friend) and family location (in Poland or the country of origin). Figure 10 presents an example of the vignette shown to people completing the survey.

Figure 11. Results from hiring choice experiment (Average Marginal Effects).
Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025). N=1,013.

As Figure 11 shows, respondents were generally less likely to hire candidates from Uzbekistan than from Ukraine. Among candidates from Uzbekistan, male candidates had a slightly lower likelihood of being hired than female candidates. The length of stay in Poland also influenced hiring preferences – Poles were more willing to hire migrant workers who had resided in Poland for five years in comparison to those with shorter lengths of residence. Similarly, having a personal recommendation significantly increased the likelihood of being chosen. Having family members in Poland positively affected respondents' willingness to hire a candidate, especially for female candidates.

Figure 12. Attribute preference by gender of respondents, hiring choice experiment (Marginal Means).
 Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025). N=1,013.

As shown in Figure 12, some differences in attribute preference (through the analysis of marginal means) emerged among male and female respondents. Male respondents perceived candidates from Ukraine positively and workers from Uzbekistan negatively; candidates from the Philippines were also perceived positively but this was not statistically significant. Women tended to view candidates from the Philippines positively, unlike workers from Uzbekistan and Ukraine who were viewed more negatively (however, not statistically significantly). The novelty of Philippines workers in Poland and their rather small numbers (Wanicka, 2025; Wanicka and Patzer, 2024) may act in their favour, compared to the other mentioned groups, especially Ukrainians who were increasingly portrayed in a negative way and seen as competitors in different spheres. Both male and female respondents had similar preferences regarding the length of residence and the location of family members. Female respondents, however, put more emphasis on recommendation status than male respondents.

Figure 13. Attribute preference by age group of respondents, hiring choice experiment (Marginal Means).
 Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025). N=1,013.

Some dissimilarities were also observed concerning the age groups of survey respondents (Figure 13). In terms of origin, candidates from Uzbekistan were more negatively perceived by younger respondents. The 40–64 group had a particularly negative attitude towards candidates from Uzbekistan. They had a positive preference for candidates from the Philippines, similarly to the youngest group (yet not statistically significant). The youngest respondents had more pronounced preferences for length of residence and recommendation status, whereas the location of the family was more important to the 40–64 age group.

The country of origin appeared to play a significant role in the hiring preferences among some groups representing different political affiliations (see Figure 14). Respondents voting for all four differentiated party subgroups (the United Right, Third Way, Civic Coalition and Other) tended to have a negative preference for the candidate from Uzbekistan, although this was only significant for United Right and Civic Coalition respondents. Even if not statistically significant, those voting for United Right and Third Way parties were more positive about candidates from Ukraine, while Civic Coalition voters preferred migrants from the Philippines. Among Coalition voters, length of residence appeared to be preferred in their selection of candidates than among other voter groups (also positive but not significant for Other voters). Recommendation status and location of the family were relevant for Civic Coalition, Third Way and United Right respondents.

The same analytical method of data analysis was applied as in Section 4.3.1. Figures 16–20 present the results, where data points to the left of the dotted line indicate a negative effect/preference, while data points to the right indicate a positive effect/preference and any data points crossing the dotted line indicate non-significant results.

Figure 16. Results from perceptions of integration experiment, all profiles (Average Marginal Effects).
Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025). N=926.

The study shows that, overall, the country of origin of the profile did not have an effect on the assessment of integration (see Figure 16). Stating the reasons for migration was perceived more positively for integration than providing no reason – and economic migration motives were evaluated slightly less favourably than education or protection motives. A lack of language proficiency and having friends and family members remaining in the country of origin negatively affected respondents’ evaluations of integration. It is important to note that the effect of the individual attributes varied by the origin of the profile (Figure 17). For example, the economic route of migration did not have an effect on evaluations of integration for the profile from India (and the protection category had a lower positive effect), religious practice was linked to positive evaluations of integration for the profile from Ukraine, while the location of friends and family in the country of origin was linked to slightly more negative evaluations for the profile from India.

Figure 17. Results from perceptions of integration experiment, by origin of profile (Average Marginal Effects). Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025). N=926.

Looking at preferences across gender groups (Figure 18), the survey indicates that respondents' gender may be linked to some, though minor, differences in perceptions of integration. Men perceived the integration of Ukrainian migrants more positively but this was not significant. Women were generally more negative when the reason for migration was not specified and tended to evaluate migration for educational purposes more positively, whereas male respondents responded more favourably to migration for protection. A lack of language proficiency and the location of friends and family in the country of origin were assessed more negatively by women than men.

Figure 18. Attribute preference by gender of respondents, perceptions of integration experiment (Marginal Means).
Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025). N=926.

Evaluations of integration by respondents' age group is presented in Figure 19. There are a few attributes worth noting here that are linked to differentiated preferences. The origin from Ukraine was more related to the positive assessment of integration among the middle-aged group, whereas the Indian origin was for the two younger groups of respondents (<65) but these preferences were not statistically significant. Having no reason for migration was linked to negative preferences for all the groups – and significantly so for the oldest respondents. Economic reasons for migration were seen negatively only for the youngest group but were not significant. Among the oldest, education was perceived less favourably than education (neither significantly), unlike in other groups. Respondents in the middle-aged group had a positive preference for education as a route for migration. In all groups the evaluation of integration was positively linked to language fluency and the location of friends and family in the survey country. Middle-aged respondents expressed a positive preference for profiles being single. Respondents in the oldest age group expressed a positive preference for religious practice in their evaluation of integration.

Figure 19. Attribute preference by age group of respondents, perceptions of integration experiment (Marginal Means). Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025). N=926.

Finally, when analysing the results by political preference (Figure 20), we can see the preference of United Right and Third Way voters for Ukrainian migrants and that of Other voters for Indian employees; however, as these data points cross the dotted lines, these are not significant. Among the reasons for migration, education was particularly positively evaluated by United Right voters, while protection was positively evaluated by Other voters (although this is difficult to analyse further given the category’s heterogeneity). Language fluency and the presence of family members or friends in Poland positively influenced the assessment of integration across all groups although the location was less salient for United Right voters. A lack of fluency was linked to negative preferences mostly for Civic Coalition voters, while having relatives or friends remaining in the country of origin was linked to negative preferences mainly among Civic Coalition and Third Way voters.

Figure 20. Attribute preference by party affiliation of respondents, perceptions of integration experiment (Marginal Means). Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025). N=926.

5 Conclusion

This report offers new insights into how the Polish public perceives irregular migration and migrants in situations of irregularity. The findings reveal several patterns: the shaping of opinions on irregular migration under the influence of political and media narratives, the impact of age and, to a lesser extent, the gender of respondents, the relativity of acceptance depending on social distance (job roles of migrants) and differences in the assessment of integration conditioned by the origins of migrants. Another notable trend is the lack of support for profiles of Ukrainian origin, particularly among women and adults aged 18–39. Although Ukrainian nationals constitute the largest and most familiar group of foreign workers in Poland, the survey results indicate shifting public attitudes, a phenomenon also observed in other studies showing a decline in sympathy toward Ukrainians (Omyła-Rudzka, 2025) and a decrease in support for accepting Ukrainian refugees (Scovil, 2025c).

Although migration in general is not perceived as a key concern, irregular migration is regarded as a significant challenge by 77.2% of respondents. Opinions on the costs and benefits of migration, as well as its impact on Polish culture, are divided. While more respondents, particularly women, believe that migration places a burden on the Polish system rather than contributes to it, views on its cultural impact were more mixed. More negative opinions about the impact of migration on Polish culture were noticeable among younger adults (aged 18–39).

Our research shows that respondents significantly overestimate the number of irregularised migrants (almost 80% overestimated the number by more than 10%). In contrast, estimates suggest that people with irregular residence status may account for roughly between 1.2%–9.9% of the foreign-born population in Poland. Irregularity is primarily seen through the lens of border crossings, applications for international protection and being hired by recruitment companies, rather than as a consequence of visa overstay or being born as a child of migrants without residence status. This reflects the influence of political and media narratives which, particularly since the 2021 humanitarian crisis on the Polish–Belarusian border began, have tended to feature more migration topics and to portray migrants as a threat – often in a dehumanising way – as tools used by the Belarusian and Russian regimes. These narratives frequently frame irregular migration as a security threat or the cause of the ‘crisis’, reinforcing public misconceptions about its scale and underlying causes (Homel-Ficenes and Grzymała-Kazłowska, 2025).

The survey also informs our understanding of how migrants with an irregular status are perceived in the context of the labour market. The majority of respondents (54.7%) said that work should be allowed for migrants with legal residence and for those undertaking work that fills market gaps. Our respondents associated irregular employment mainly with construction, renovation, agriculture, transportation, food delivery and taxi driving for men – and with cleaning, catering and hospitality, childcare and elderly care, retail and sex work for women. When it came to jobs that involve more temporary and public interactions, such as work in shops or restaurants, the legal status of migrants was seen as less important than in the context of work performed within respondents’ homes or at their workplace.

In the hiring-choice experiment, the results show visible differences depending on the country of origin. In general, candidate workers from Uzbekistan were viewed the least positively. There were differences in national-origin preferences among genders, with female respondents expressing positive preferences towards candidates from the Philippines and male respondents having the most positive preference for the

Ukrainian candidates – but a negative preference towards the one from Uzbekistan. There was a negative attitude towards hiring someone from Uzbekistan among respondents under 65 years old. Respondents from the middle-aged group had a positive preference for hiring a candidate from the Philippines, while all groups showed a (non-significant) positive preference for a worker from Ukraine. United Right and Civic Coalition voters expressed a negative preference for the candidate from Uzbekistan.

In many instances, although this varied by subgroup, there were positive connotations with longer residence, presence of personal recommendation and having family in Poland, while there were negative connotations with shorter residence, no recommendations and family in the country of origin.

The experiment on the perception of integration showed some impact of attributed otherness for assessing migrants' integration, as certain attributes for someone from India were evaluated slightly more negatively than those for an irregularised migrant from Ukraine. Yet, no very clear country-of-origin effects were observed among subgroups; however, it is worth mentioning that male respondents evaluated the integration of Ukrainian migrants more favourably than did females.

The included attributes turned out to have a considerable influence on the perception of integration. There was a clear negative effect of the lack of information on migration motives and on language fluency. Among the reasons provided for migration, all were positive but improvement in living standards was seen the least favourably. Seeking protection received a slightly less positive assessment than migration for educational purposes, particularly among women, younger respondents (<65) and voters for United Right and Third Way. This may be related both to the recent, unprecedented increase in involuntary migration to Poland following Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine and to the Polish–Belarusian humanitarian crisis, as well as the negative media images of migrants overusing protection mechanisms. As the IPSOS (2025) survey indicates, while Poles generally support accepting people seeking protection, they remain sceptical about refugees' ability to successfully integrate into Polish society. It is interesting to compare our results on perceptions of integration with the recent findings on models of integration in Poland (Scovil, 2025a). The CBOS study shows that, among the three approaches to integration – assimilation, moderately multicultural and separation – Poles generally favoured the assimilation model, which encompasses expectations that migrants should conform to Polish culture and social norms. It was also observed that, when evaluating integration, Poles place greater emphasis on Polish language proficiency and the length of residence in Poland (Scovil, 2025a).

To summarise, the survey results reveal the complexity of current trends in public perceptions of irregular migration in Poland, with particularly distinctive patterns seen among women and younger respondents. The findings also underscore the significant impact of political narratives and media representations in shaping public knowledge about irregular migration, which is often presented as an exaggerated threat and as reinforcing stereotypical negative portrayals of migrants and contributing to othering. This highlights the importance of public debate and the active involvement of experts and the quality press in reshaping narratives about irregular migration, its causes, its conditions and its scale.

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Appendices

Table A.1 Overview of the content of the I-CLAIM survey

Section	Description of question
A. Overall concerns	Top issues facing the country today
	Top issues facing you personally
B. Attitudes and experience toward immigration	Close friends as immigrants (split allocation)
	Whether immigrants take more in or out of society
	Whether cultural like undermined or enriched by immigrants
	Views on immigrants and work
C. Perception of irregular migration/migrants	Percentage of irregular migrants in country
	Whether irregular migration is a concern in country
	Work sector for female irregular migrants
	Work sector for male irregular migrants
	Scenarios of irregularity
D. Attitudes toward irregular migration and work/employment	List experiment on policy deservingness for female cleaner
	Conjoint experiment – <i>female care workers</i>
	Likelihood of hiring applicant 1
	Likelihood of hiring applicant 2
	Choice of applicant
	Conjoint experiment – <i>male care workers</i>
	Likelihood of hiring applicant 1
	Likelihood of hiring applicant 2
	Choice of applicant
	Factorial experiment – <i>Perceptions of integration for male irregular migrant 1</i>
	Factorial experiment – <i>Perceptions of integration for male irregular migrant 2</i>
	Social distance indicator – <i>3 scenarios</i>
E. Further demographics	Immigrant generation
	Religiosity
	Member of ethnic minority group
	Has lived outside of country for over 1 year

Table A.2: Main Respondent Demographics (N=1,013)

Characteristic	Categories	%
Age (N=1,013)	Adult (18-39)	41.7%
	Middle Age (40-64)	30.6%
	Older adults (65+)	27.7%
Gender (N=1,013)	Male	48.8%
	Female	51.2%
Ethnic Minority (N= 956)	No	95.2%
	Yes	4.8%
Marital Status (N= 995)	Married, partnership, living as married, in a relationship	69.7%
	Divorced, widowed, separated	11.8%
	Not in a relationship	18.5%
Location (N=1,013)	Urban	48%
	Suburban, rural	52%
Region (N=1,013)	PL1 REGION CENTRALNY	21.5%
	PL2 REGION POŁUDNIOWY	20.3%
	PL3 REGION WSCHODNI	17.5%
	PL4 REGION PÓŁNOCNO-ZACHODNI	15.8%
	PL5 REGION POŁUDNIOWO-ZACHODNI	10.1%
	PL6 REGION PÓŁNOCNY	14.8%

Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025).

Table A.3: Respondents' Socio-Demographics

Characteristic	Categories	%
Education level (N=1,013)	Low	9.7%
	Medium	65.9%
	High	24.5%
Work status (N=1,013)	Working	53.7%
	Not working	46.3%
Household income (N=863)	Low	29.5%
	Medium	40.1%
	High	30.4%
Party voted for in 2023 (N=1,013)	Law and Justice/ United Right	29.9%
	Civic Coalition	25.2%
	The Left	8%
	The Third Way (Poland 2050 and Polish Peasant Party)	12%
	Confederation	5.9%
	Other response	3.1%
	Don't know, invalid vote	15.8%

Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025).

Table A.4: Respondents' Links to migration

Characteristic	Categories	%
Country of birth (N=994)	Outside of Poland	3%
	Poland	97%
Immigrant parentage (N=990)	None	86.7%
	One parent	4%
	Two parents	9.3%
Experience of migration (N=982)	No	87%
	Yes	13%
Has immigrant friends (N=984)	None	66.4%
	Yes, several	12.6%
	Yes, a few	21%

Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025).

Table A.5 Attributes for hiring experiment randomly selected for each profile.

COUNTRY OF ORIGIN: FEMALE NAME/MALE NAME Two of three chosen for the female and male candidates.	Ukraine: Polina/Artem Uzbekistan: Medina/Akmal Philippines: Gloria/Jose
LENGTH OF RESIDENCE One of two.	under a year 5 years
RECOMMENDATION STATUS One of two.	<no recommendation> but comes recommended by a friend
LOCATION OF FAMILY One of two.	Country of origin Survey country

Table A.6 Attributes for integration experiments randomly selected for each profile.

COUNTRY OF ORIGIN/NAME One for each profile	Ukraine: Ivan India: Ram
REASON FOR MIGRATION One of four.	<no reason stated> to improve his living standards to get an education to seek protection
SURVEY COUNTRY LANGUAGE FLUENCY One of two.	speaks does not speak
RELIGIOSITY One of two.	He regularly practices his religion. <none stated>
LOCATION OF FRIENDS One of two.	From COUNTRY OF ORIGIN From SURVEY COUNTRY
FAMILY STATUS One of two.	He is single He has a family
LOCATION OF FAMILY If has family One of two.	In COUNTRY OF ORIGIN In SURVEY COUNTRY

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Improving the Living
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Households in Europe